

TABLE I

Sl. No.	Complex	Colour	Carbon%		Hydrogen%		Nitrogen%		Metal%	
			Cal.	Found	Cal.	Found	Cal.	Found	Cal.	Found
1.	$\text{Fe}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N})_3$	Blue	73.82	74.20	4.10	4.00	4.78	4.93	6.37	6.58
2.	$\text{Cr}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N})_3$	Dark blue	74.14	74.86	4.12	4.21	4.80	5.19	5.94	5.73

complexes with d^5 and d^3 systems having one unpaired electron only.

The molar conductance (ΔM) values of the Fe(III) and Cr(III) complexes in dioxane was found to be 1.4 and 1.8 mhos respectively shows the non-electrolytic nature of the chelates. I. R. spectral data reveals that the lowering in $-\text{OH}$ and $-\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ stretching frequencies at 3250 and 1665 cm^{-1} of parent ligand on complexation. This lowering indicates the participation of these groups in co-ordination. $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ group being at remoter position does not participate in the metal ligand interaction because the band corresponding to $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ groups remains unperturbed during chelation. New bands appear in the ligand complexes with Fe(III) at 345 cm^{-1} and 436 cm^{-1} whereas in Cr(III) at 285 cm^{-1} and 423 cm^{-1} respectively fairly attributable to metal-oxygen and metal-nitrogen bonds which is in accordance with the results of Poddar and Das⁹.

Taking into accounts the above results, most probable formula assigned to the complexes are.

$\text{M}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N})_3$ where $\text{M} = \text{Fe}(\text{III})$ and $\text{Cr}(\text{III})$. Above structure satisfies maximum co-ordination number six for Fe(III) and Cr(III).

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Application of Radius Ratio Criterion to the Stability of Pyrochlore in Some Mixed Metal Oxide Systems

V. S. DARSHANE

Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Institute of Science, Bombay-400 032

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LITERATURE survey revealed that very little work is reported on pyrochlores where substitution of cations is carried out at A as well as B sites. Analysis¹ of natural pyrochlore minerals suggest that wide variety of both cationic and anionic substitutions are possible. Therefore, the systems $\text{Y}_{2-x}\text{Ca}_x\text{Ti}_{2-y}\text{Nb}_y\text{O}_7$, $\text{La}_{2-x}\text{Ca}_x\text{Zr}_{2-y}\text{Nb}_y\text{O}_7$ and $\text{La}_{2-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{Zr}_{2-y}\text{Nb}_y\text{O}_7$ were studied by X-ray powder diffraction technique in order to investigate limits on the possibilities of ionic substitution (limiting radius ratio). Here it is observed that radius ratio criterion seems to be relatively unimportant in determining the stability limit for pyrochlore structure.

Pyrochlore compounds in which substitution of cations taking place either at A or B sites have been reported by various workers²⁻¹¹. Pyrochlore structure has the general formula $\text{A}_2\text{B}_2\text{O}_7$ where A ions retain the eightfold co-ordination while B ions are only in sixfold co-ordination. Thus A ion is larger than B ion in the pyrochlore structure. The pyrochlore space group is found to be $\text{Fd}3\text{M}-\text{O}_h^7$ and there are eight $\text{A}_2\text{B}_2\text{O}_7$ formula units in the pyrochlore unit cell.

All the compositions mentioned in Table I were prepared by using standard ceramic technique and X-ray diffractometer patterns were taken on Philips X-ray machine using $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation with Nickel filter. The results of X-ray analysis are given in Table I.

From Table I it is observed that in the systems investigated, the single pyrochlore phase is observed up to the compositions $\text{Y}_{1.6}\text{Ca}_{0.4}\text{Ti}_{1.6}\text{Nb}_{0.4}\text{O}_7$, $\text{La}_{0.8}\text{Ca}_{1.2}\text{Zr}_{0.8}\text{Nb}_{1.2}\text{O}_7$ and $\text{La}_{1.4}\text{Sr}_{0.6}\text{Zr}_{1.4}\text{Nb}_{0.6}\text{O}_7$. Knop *et al*⁶ while studying pyrochlore titanates of the type $\text{Y}_{2-x}\text{Ln}_x\text{Ti}_2\text{O}_7$ (where Ln = lanthanide ion from Sm to Lu) have observed the stability limit extending from Ahrens radius ratio of nearly 1.22 to 1.50. In the case of pyrochlore Stannates⁷ they have reported the lower limit of $[r(\text{A}^{3+})/r(\text{Sn}^{4+})]$ 1.19 (Ahrens) and upper limit

TABLE 1

Formula	Radius ratio	Phases present
1. $Y_2Ti_2O_7$	1.353 (1.672)	Pyrochlore $a=10.08 \text{ \AA}$
2. $(Y_{1-x}Ca_x)_2(Ti_{1-y}Nb_y)_2O_7$ x and y=0.2	1.370 (1.690)	Pyrochlore $a=10.12 \text{ \AA}$
3. $(Y_{1-x}Ca_x)_2(Ti_{1-y}Nb_y)_2O_7$ x and y=0.3	1.380 (1.694)	Pyrochlore $a=10.17 \text{ \AA}$ + Calcium niobate (Monoclinic) trace
4. $Ca_2Nb_2O_7$	1.435 (1.750)	Monoclinic ^{1,2}
5. $La_2Zr_2O_7$	1.443 (1.639)	Pyrochlore $a=10.80 \text{ \AA}$
6. $(La_{1-x}Ca_x)_2(Zr_{1-y}Nb_y)_2O_7$ x and y=0.6	1.438 (1.702)	Pyrochlore $a=10.59 \text{ \AA}$
7. $(La_{1-x}Ca_x)_2(Zr_{1-y}Nb_y)_2O_7$ x and y=0.7	1.437 (1.713)	Pyrochlore $a=10.57 \text{ \AA}$ + Cal. niobate (trace)
8. $(La_{1-x}Sr_x)_2(Zr_{1-y}Nb_y)_2O_7$ x and y=0.3	1.492 (1.726)	Pyrochlore $a=10.77 \text{ \AA}$
9. $(La_{1-x}Sr_x)_2(Zr_{1-y}Nb_y)_2O_7$ x and y=0.4	1.510 (1.756)	Pyrochlore $a=10.75 \text{ \AA}$ + $Sr_2Nb_2O_7$ (trace)
10. $Sr_2Nb_2O_7$	1.624 (1.953)	Monoclinic ^{1,2}

N. B. Radius ratios are calculated by using Ahrens radii for comparison with other workers while the values reported in parenthesis are obtained by using Shannon and Prewitt^{1,4} ionic radii.

1.61. In calculating radius ratio Ahrens ionic radii are used for comparison with other workers. Similarly Wilson¹¹ has also calculated limiting radius ratio for 3-4 (valence of cation at A site is three while that of at B site is four) as well as 2-5 pyrochlores. It is between 1.18 and 1.63.

Now if the radius ratios reported by Knop and Brisse⁶⁻⁷ and Wilson¹¹ are applied to the systems investigated in Table 1, then all the compositions except $Sr_2Nb_2O_7$ ($r_A/r_B=1.624$) should have shown pyrochlore structure. From the systems investigated by Brisse it can be concluded that radius ratio rule applies fairly well, if the substitution is carried out either at A or B site but when the substitutions are carried out at A as well as B sites and ions of different charges are used, the radius ratio criterion does not apply. In fact use of ions carrying different charges (in order to compensate valence changes) should have induced fields with lower symmetry causing distortion of the pyrochlore structure. But it is observed that the structure is not distorted but at certain critical concentration, which varies from system to system, formation of solid solution is prohibited forming two distinct crystallographic phases. Therefore, it can be concluded that when cations of different charges and radii are substituted at both the sites, radius ratio criterion seems to be relatively unimportant in determining the stability limit for pyrochlore structure.

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3-Aldehydosalicyledene Cyanoacetyl Hydrazone as a New Reagent for the Spectrophotometric Determination of Ferric Ions*

K. K. PANDE* and J. V. LIKHAR

Chemistry Department, Govt. Science College, Gwalior, M. P.
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WHILE a number of compounds have been investigated as a reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of ferric ions. 3-Aldehydosalicyledene cyanoacetyl hydrazone (3-ASCAH) has not been investigated so far for this purpose. Fe^{3+} -3-ASCAH system was found to give stable reddish brown colour in acidic medium. The present article reports the use of 3-ASCAH as a new sensitive analytical reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of ferric ions at 370 nm in a pH range 4 to 5 and 50% ethanol-aqueous medium.

Experimental

Materials: All reagent and chemicals used in the present work were of Analar B.D.H. grade. Pure distilled water redistilled over alkaline permanganate and free from carbon dioxide, was used throughout the investigation.

Synthesis of Ligand: The 3-aldehydosalicylic acid and cyanoacetic acid hydrazide were prepared^{1,2} and taken in equimolecular proportions in

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